

Research

Hydrochemical Evaluation of the spring water suitability for drinking purpose at Sheringal, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

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Abstract: The objective of this study was to explore lake and land breezes over the Lake Victoria basin based on 2 years (2019 to 2020). Hourly and daily data of wind speed and direction, precipitation, 2-meter air temperature over land, and Lake mix-layer depth obtained from Era 5 re-analysis were utilized. The method employed was based on the characteristics of the lake breeze with the elimination of the days with strong synoptic winds. According to the results, the main drivers for the breeze development at the meteorological stations were the thermal gradient between the lake and the surroundings and the low-level winds. The breezes mainly occur between 9:00 h and 15:00 h characterized by divergence over the lake and reduction in temperature and they move over land. The study calls for a look at the factors that may contribute to the formation of the breezes.

Keywords: Victoria basin, Breeze, Era5, Uganda

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Introduction

Water covers about 71% of earth surface and is one of the most significant natural resources upon which all living things depend. Water is a renewable natural resource spread through the hydrological cycle and causes the develop-

ment and destruction of great civilizations in the world by their presence and deficit. Natural water is a universal solvent with various impurities added by different processes such as weathering, leaching, dissolution, mining, agricultural fertilizers, industries, and organic matter.

People in every part of the world are affected, either directly or indirectly, by such accumulated contaminants, which render water unfit for drinking and unsuitable for agriculture purposes. Similarly, water destroyed human populations and other organisms through diseases and flooding throughout the earth's history (Trivedi & Raj, 1992). Surface water and groundwater are major sources of water on the earth (Van der Perk, 2013).

Except for the oceans and seas, all ground-based sources of water are considered surface water. The water is clear and fresh near the surface, so sunlight may easily pass through. Photosynthesis, which requires oxygen and light, occurs in photoautotrophic plants and changes the chemical composition of water (Majid, Islam, Nap, Ghafoori, & Abdu, 2012).

Surface waters are contaminated by humans, animals, and microbial activities, adding toxic chemicals (Abioye, 2011). Toxic chemicals and heavy metals are added to the water by various domestic wastes produced by sewage systems, mining, industries, and organic activities

Groundwater is everywhere and can be accessed through a shallow or greater depths (Jasechko & Perrone, 2021). Groundwater is stored in porous rock within the earth, which is added from the surface by percolation through porous and permeable strata (Patil & Desai; Yadav, Sonje, Mathur, & Jain, 2012). The contamination of ground water occurs when solid and liquid wastes seep into the ground from the surface, where they are generated by the activities of humans, animals, industries, agriculture, mining, and sewage systems. These wastes can be either solid or liquid (Zaporozec, 1981). During the percolation of these wastes from the surface through porous strata, most toxic and harmful chemicals are filtered and removed, making them favorable for drinking purposes (Egboka, Nwankwor, Orajaka, & Ejiofor, 1989).

Although water is pure in its natural state, it is being polluted and contaminated in modern times. Both natural and anthropogenic processes pollute water; however anthropogenic processes are considered a constant polluting source of water (Singh, Malik, Mohan, & Sinha, 2004). Groundwater is not completely pure because it contains dissolved mineral ions, affecting the quality of groundwater used for different purposes (Li et al., 2016). The major ions present in excess amounts in groundwater are calcium (Ca^{2+}), Magnesium (Mg^{2+}), sodium (Na^+), potassium (K^+), bicarbonate (HCO_3^-), sulfates (SO_4^{2-}), Chloride (Cl^-), non-ionic constituents such as oxides, phenols, synthetic detergents and dissolved gases such as oxygen (O_2) and carbon dioxide (CO_2) (Tijani, 1994). Agricultural practices, industrial processes, air pollution, mining, sewage systems, organic activities, and the illegal dumping of solid and liquid waste all contribute to the contamination of water. This results in the addition of toxic chemicals and other microbes to water, which in turn affects the quality of water both on the surface and deep within the ground (Niemi et al., 1990).

The distribution of naturally occurring substances in water, human activities, and other natural processes also causes water contamination (Masindi & Muedi, 2018). The solid waste generated by industries is exposed to the atmosphere in dumping sites where it reacts with rain water and the surface runoff, which dissolve chemicals and other microbes and then percolate it downward and contaminate groundwater (Polubarinova-Koch, 2015).

Geological strata, the lithological composition of rocks, the type of the soil, and the water circulation pattern via the pore spaces are some of the other factors that might influence the quality of groundwater (Kohlhepp et al., 2017; Singhal & Gupta, 2010). Generally, the quality of groundwater depends on the chemical composition of recharge water, the interaction of water and soil, the soil-gas interaction in a particular system such as an aquifer, and the interaction of water with the rocks of the saturated zone. The residence time of water in an aquifer and the chemical reaction in the pore spaces (Böhlke, 2002; Nwankwoala).

Moreover, the eutrophication processes of photosynthetic plants such as algae in the water, the activities of the microbial organism, decomposition of organic matter, and pressure and temperature conditions also alter water chemistry and thus pollute the groundwater (Ramanathan et al., 2004).

Considering the above scenario of ground water, the present study focuses on analyzing the physiochemical characteristics of spring water in the Sheringal area to determine the concentration of pollutants and other toxic chemicals.

Location of the study area

The study area is located in Dir Upper near Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University Sheringal at latitude 35°16'12" .71N and longitude 72°00'9" .44E (Figure 1). The study area is easily accessible from Peshawar through the Peshawar-Malakand-Dir road. Onward from Dir, a new road has been constructed which enters Sheringal valley through Babe Kumrat and is about 20 km from Chokyatton to Sheringal.

Climate

The weather in the study area is moderate to extreme. January's maximum and minimum temperature has been recorded as 11.220 C0 and -3.60 C0 in high elevation areas, with snow falling from November until April. July is the warmest month, with an average temperature of 30C0 at noontime. September and November are the driest months. Less amount of rainfall occurs in these two months. Annually about 1430 mm of rain fall occurs.

Figure 1: Google earth map of the study area showing sample sites in the study area.

Regional Geological Setting

The tectonic history of Pakistan can be traced back to the late Paleozoic, in which the continents were present in the form of a continuous land mass, "Pangaea," surrounded by an ocean Panthalassa (Smith & Hallam, 1970; Suess, 1981; Wegner, 1924). Pangaea split into southern Gondwanaland and northern Laurasian subcontinents in Triassic times and was separated by the Paleo-Tethys seaway (Du Toit, 1937).

In Late Permo-Triassic time, the Karakoram block detached from Gondwana's drifted towards the north and accreted with Laurasian along its southern margin in the Mesozoic and early Tertiary times (Gaetani, Grove, & Bryan, 1993; Golonka, 2004). The detachment of the Karakoram block from Gondwana's causes the closer of Paleo-Tethys to the south and the formation of Neo-Tethys towards the north of the Gondwana's through the process of Seafloor spreading (Golonka, 2004).

About 130 million years ago, the Indo-Pakistan crustal plate rifted from Gondwana's motherland and drifted towards the north, initially (between 130 and 80 Ma) at a rate of 3 to 5 cm/year, 16 cm/year between 50-80 Ma and 15-25 cm/year after 50 Ma, supported by sea-floor spreading along Mid Indian Ocean Ridge and transform faulting along

the Proto-Owen fracture zone (Johnson et al., 1982; Powell, 1979). The drifting of the Indian Plate towards the north causes the shrinking of the Neo-Tethys ocean because of the generation of intra-oceanic subduction zones, which in turn resulted from the formation of volcanic island arcs (Kohistan-Ladakh-Nuristan-Kandhar) in early cretaceous time (Searle, 1991; Treloar & Izatt, 1993). In the mid cretaceous (102-85), the K.I.A. collided with Eurasia along its southern margin, known as Northern Megashear or the Main Karakoram Thrust (M.K.T.) or shyoke suture, and formed Andean-type continental margin (Figure. 2) (Khan et al., 2009; Petterson, Windley, & Sullivan, 1990; TAHIRKHELI, 1979; Treloar & Izatt, 1993). While In Eocene time (55-50) the Indian Plate collided with K.I.A. along its northern margin known as Indus suture, MMT or Indus Psangpo suture zone (Figure. 2) (O'brien, Zotov, Law, Khan, & Jan, 2001; TAHIRKHELI, 1979).

Figure 2: Regional tectonic map of Pakistan showing the major fault systems in northern Pakistan. (after (Parsons, Yeats, Yagi, & Hussain, 2006)

Methodology

Sampling

During fieldwork, water samples from different springs were collected. G.P.S. points were taken on every sample point to plot it on a Google earth map (Fig. 1). Sample 1 was taken from Sheringal Bazar, sample 2 was taken from Sea Shoor, sample 3 was taken from Gaday (Samang), sample 4 was taken from the main gate of S.B.B.U, and sample 5 was taken from Samang Mosque (Fig.1)

The water samples were taken in the distal bottle with a lid at the top and then brought to P.C.S.I.R. lab Peshawar to conduct the physiochemical analyses of each sample.

In physiochemical analyses, we find 12 parameters of each sample which are as follows.

Total dissolved solids (T.D.S.).

The total amount of organic and inorganic substances present in water can pass through a 2-micron filter. The water samples were taken in beakers and recorded the T.D.S. concentration by using the electrode L.A. Lutron WA2015. The water in the beakers was continuously stirred, and the readings were noted on their stability in beaker

Conductivity

It is the measurement of electric current Conductivity through the water. It is measured by using a portable conductivity probe and meter. E.C. of each sample was recorded using a Mettler Toledo MC 226 conductivity meter. The probe was dipped in water, the E.C. meter was switched on, and the readings were recorded in (μS)/cm.

Total hardness as CaCo_3

Water is a universal solvent, so it has dissolved minerals such as calcium and Magnesium derived from rocks and soil. As the water passes through rocks and soil, it dissolves these ions and then transports them to the ground water supply, making the water hard.

$$\text{Total Hardness} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{L}} \right) = \text{Ca}^{+2} \text{hardness} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{L}} \right) + \text{Mg}^{+2} \text{hardness} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{L}} \right) \text{ Eq. 10}$$

Hardness Buffer, E.B.T. (Erichrome Black T) indicator, and EDTA are the chemicals required for calculating hardness. Wash all glass wares. Take a 10 ml sample in a clean titration flask. Add 1 ml hardness Buffer and a pinch of E.B.T. as an indicator. Now titrate this solution against the EDTA solution. Take the difference between the initial and final reading of EDTA used.

$$\text{Calculations Total Hardness in } \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{L}} = \frac{\text{mlofEDTAused}}{\text{mlofsample}} \times 1000 \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

Where,

$$\text{mlofEDTAused} = \text{Finalreading} - \text{Initialreadin}$$

Total suspended solid (T.S.S.)

Total suspended solids (T.S.S.) represent the concentration of suspended solid particles in water. The suspended solid concentration makes the water turbid, defined by its milky or muddy appearance in the presence of light. Contaminated water contains fine suspended solid particles with very low density and does not settle to the bottom at normal conditions.

To find out the T.S.S. in water filter paper of known weight is taken, and one liter of sample water is allowed to pass through it. The filter paper is then dried out completely by placing a lamp above it. After that, the weight of the filter paper and any increase in the weight of the filter paper represent total suspended solid in water measured in ppm per liter of water.

Determination of Sodium and Potassium (Na + K)

In order to determine the amount of sodium and potassium present in the water, a standard stock solution with a concentration of 1000 mg/l is created by dissolving 2.542 grams of sodium chloride and 1.907 grams of potassium chloride in deionized water. In order to lessen the concentration of the solution, one liter of doubly deionized water is added to the volumetric flask.

After taking several separate samples from a stock solution with varying concentrations, such as 2.5 gm/l, 5 gm/l, and 10 gm/l, the samples were then diluted by adding doubly de-ionized water on an as-needed basis.. The instrument was adjusted to the above condition and calibrated with a standard stock solution.

Chloride as Cl

To find the Chlorides (Cl) concentration in water, "H.A.C.H. DR 2800 photometer was used. 70 gm chlorides were taken for this purpose. Two cells were selected for this experiment; in one cell, 10 ml of de-ionized water was taken and kept blank; in the second cell, 10 ml of sample was taken, and 0.8 ml of Mercuric Thio-cyanate solution was used added to both cells, and mixed it completely. After that, 0.4 ml of ferric ion solution was added to each cell, and an orange color appeared in each cell after complete mixing. The cells are then kept for a while to complete the reaction, and the result was observed in mg/l.

Principle

Sulfate ions (SO₄²⁻) react with barium chloride (BaCl₂) and form barium sulfate (BaSO₄). BaSO₄ suspended in water is measured by spectrophotometer, and the sulfate concentration is measured by comparison of reading with a standard curve.

Sulfate buffer and Barium chloride solution are required for this experiment. Take 20 ml of sample in a titration flask after filtration and 20 ml of distilled water in another flask. Add 1ml sulfate buffer and barium chloride to both samples and shake the contents to dissolve completely. After some time, the absorbance reading appears on the spectrophotometer at 420 nm. Deduce the value of sulfates with the help of a standard curve, and the results were noted

pH

Ph represents the acidity and basicity of a solution. The Ph scale shows the concentration of the H⁺ ions and OH⁻ ions in an aqueous solution. It is represented by the negative logarithm of the active hydrogen ion concentration in an aqueous solution.

$$pH = \frac{1}{\log \text{hydrogenionconcentration} \frac{\text{mole}}{\text{liter}}} \tag{Eq. 1}$$

$$pH = \frac{1}{\log \text{hydrogenionconcentration} (\text{molL}^{-1})} \tag{Eq. 2}$$

If the H⁺ ion concentration changes by a factor of ten, the pH value changes by one unit.

$$pH = \frac{1}{\log 10} \tag{Eq. 3}$$

Each sample's pH was recorded using the "L.A. Lutron WA-2015" pH meter.

Each sample was stirred thoroughly using a fresh glass stirring rod, and the pH value was recorded simultaneously.

Alkalinity

Alkalinity refers to the capacity of water to neutralize the acid. The buffer solution is a type of solution which shows resistance to its ions concentration (H⁺ ions). The excess H⁺ ions are absorbed, and the pH of water remains constant in the buffer solution. The carbonate ions are added to the system by calcium and magnesium carbonates. Alkalinity reflects the hardness of water caused by carbonate mineral concentration. In contrast, soft water has a low concentration of carbonate ions. It thus has low Alkalinity and little buffering capacity, which show variation in pH due to acid rain and acid accumulation.

A computer-aided titrimeter (C.A.T.) and the pH electrode measure alkalinity. Potentiometric titration is taken to an end-point reading of pH 4.5. The amount of acid required to reach a pH of 4.5 is expressed in milliliters. The calcium ions (Ca²⁺) neutralize the acid in this reaction, showing the sample's buffering capacity. The amount of used acid in this experiment indicates the amount of carbonate (Co₃) in the water.

Determination of Calcium and Magnesium (Ca+Mg)

The preparation of standard stock solutions of 1000 mg/l of calcium and magnesium required the addition of 2.479g of calcium carbonate and 4.952g of magnesium carbonate to a volume of 50 ml of double-deionized water. A drop of HCl measuring 10 milliliters was added to the solution before being diluted with double-filtered water to remove calcium and magnesium ions. Several solutions of working standards of 2.5, 5, and 10 mg/l were isolated, and 3 ml of lanthanum oxide was added to show the concentration of Ca and Mg ions. The instrument was adjusted according to the condition and standard of the stock solution.

Results and Discussion

Physic-chemical analysis of different water samples collected from springs in the study area were analyzed in the P.C.S.I.R. laboratory. The results were compared with the standard suggested by W.H.O.

The results of the different parameters are as follows:

Total Dissolved Solids (T.D.S.)

Based on the total dissolve solid, the drinking water is divided into fresh, slight saline, moderately sa-line, very saline, and brine (Table 1). (U.S. Public health 1985).

Table.1: The comparison of different water based on dissolved solids.

1.	Less than 1,000 mg/l	Fresh
2.	1,000 – 3,000 mg/l	Slightly Saline
3.	3,000 – 10,000 mg/l	Moderately Saline
4.	10,000 – 35,000 mg/l	Very Saline
5.	More than 35,000 mg/l	Brine

Factors that control the TDS. in water include dissoluble rocks, evaporation, and disposal of solid wastes from industries and municipal sewage systems.

The TDS values of all the water samples of the study area are shown in Figure 3 and Table. 2. Which are below the WHO standard limit.

Figure 3: Bar graph compares TDS of water samples with WHO standard

Conductivity

Conductivity is the ability of water to conduct electric current, expressed in millisiemens/meter (Peavy, Rowe, & Tchobanoglous, 1985). The higher the electrical Conductivity, the higher the concentration of dissolved solids and vice versa.

The Electrical Conductivity of all water samples is shown in Figures 4 and Table.2, Which are below the W.H.O standard limit.

Figure 4: Shows the comparison of the Conductivity of water samples.

Total Hardness

The total hardness of different samples is below the permissible limit of 500mg/L (WHO, 2004), which is given in Figure 5 and Table.2.

Figure 5: illustrates the comparison of the Total hardness of water samples with WHO standard limit.

Total suspended solids

The values of total suspended solids in different samples are given in Figure 6 and table.2.

Except for sample 2, all the samples are below the WHO standards limit.

Figure 6: Showing the comparison of T.S.S. of water samples with WHO standard.

Sodium (Na)

It generally contributes to water by weathering feldspar in Igneous rock by mixings with salty connote water (Karanth, Lyson, & McCann, 1993). The concentration of Na is increased with TDS solids. Sodi-um concentration is relatively high in deep aquifers compared to shallow due to the low water velocity in a deep aquifer (Driscoll, 1986). Sodium concentration in different samples is shown in Figure 7 and Table 2. All the samples are within permissible limits and are below the WHO limits.

Figure 7: Shows the comparison of sodium of water samples with WHO standard.

Potassium as K

Potassium in the earth's crust is the major constituent of K-bearing minerals such as feldspar, mica, and clay. Its concentration in water is very less due to its very low solubility. According to (Golditech, 1938), Potassium in groundwater is derived from clay minerals. The concentrations of Potassium in all the water samples are within permissible limits. (Figure 8 and Table .2.)

Figure 8: Showing the comparison of Potassium of water samples with WHO standard.

Chloride as Cl

Chloride is widely distributed in the environment through KCl, NaCl, and CaCl₂. The weathering and leaching of sedimentary rock and dissolution of salt deposits release chloride in water. Naturally also occurs in groundwater in deep aquifers because of pollution from seawater industry wastes (Zaporozec, 1981).

The chloride concentrations in a different sample are shown in Figure 9 and Table 2, which show values within the permissible limits.

Figure 9: Showing the comparison of Chloride in water samples with W.H.O standard.

Sulphate as SO₄

The concentration in groundwater is caused by the natural deposit of sodium sulfate and magnesium sulfate. Also, the oxidation of sulfur ore mostly dissolves in rainwater. Climate also affects the accumulation of sulfur in groundwater and soil. The sulfate accumulates (both in surface and groundwater) with low percolation. According to US-EPA (1978) and WHO (1984). The SO_4 concentrations in various samples are low and under the permissible limit of the W.H.O standard (Figure 10 and table 2.)

Figure 10: Showing the comparison of sulfate in water samples with WHO standard.

P.H.

It measures the acidity of a solution or the negative log of hydrogen ion concentration in a solution. The pH values of water generally range from 4 to 9, which the later represent, bicarbonate and car-bonates concentration in water (hard water) (Burgelman, Nollet, & Degrave, 2000).

The pH value of all samples does not vary greatly from the mean pH value and is under the permissible limits of the WHO standard (Figure 11 and Table.2).

Figure 11: Showing the comparison of pH of water samples with W.H.O standard.

Total Alkalinity

It is the ability of water to neutralize acid caused by carbonates and bicarbonate ions accumulation. Bi-carbonate ions in groundwater are added from the carbon dioxide in the atmosphere and soil and dis-solution of carbonate rocks (Pearson Jr & Hanshaw, 1970). The total Alkalinity of all the water samples was under the permissible limits of WHO standard limit, which is shown in Figure 12 and Table.2.

Figure 12: The Alkalinity of water samples with W.H.O standard

Calcium as Ca

The important constituent of water contributes from various rocks such as gypsum, dolomite, lime-stone, and minerals such as calcite. Calcium is derived from soil and rocks, representing groundwater's solubility of calcium carbonates, sulfates, and chlorides.

Calcium is the major constituent of igneous rocks and minerals such as plagioclase, pyroxene, and amphibole, which are in appreciable amounts in soil and water. Agricultural fertilizers add Ca to the soil and water (Majid et al., 2012). Calcium concentrations of different samples (Figure 13 and Table .2.) are within permissible limits and below the WHO limits.

Figure 14. Showing the comparison of calcium in water samples and WHO standard.

Magnesium as Mg

The important constituent of water contributes to the surface and groundwater from Mg-rich rock (dolomite, gypsum) and mafic and ultramafic igneous rock. Mg concentration is generally low in the water. It depends on the rocks' nature and where they percolate and flow.

However, water having contact with mafic and ultramafic rocks has a high concentration of Magnesium. The hardness of water also occurs due to Magnesium. (US-EPA, 1978).

Mg concentrations of different samples are shown in (Figure 15 and Table .2.) Which are within permissible limits of W.H.O.

Figure 15: Showing the comparison of Magnesium of water samples with W.H.O standard

Table: 2. Comparison of different water parameters of the study area with WHO standard.

Conclusion and recommendation

The contamination of water is a threat to every community on this planet. It has been observed that the main source of

Phys- ic-Chemical Parameters	Method No.	Units	Result of samples					Expanded Un- certainty (\pm)	WHO stand- ard For Drinki ng Water
			S.01	S.02	S.03	S.04	S.05		
Total Dissolved Solids(T.D.S.)	2540. C	mg/L	457.67	307.33	358.33	436.33	369.00	-	1000.00
Conductivity	2510. B	μ S/cm	590.00	410.00	460.00	520.00	480.00	-	-
Total Hardness	2340. C	mg/L	256.42	166.03	240.47	254.65	235.23	3.33	500.00
Total Suspended Solids(T.S.S.)	2540. D	mg/L	4.67	5.00	4.67	4.00	4.67	-	5.00
Sodium as Na	3500-Na	mg/L	23.43	18.47	10.17	13.97	14.40	1.70	200.00
Potassium as K	3500-K	mg/L	6.90	7.33	0.83	2.13	2.43	0.64	75.00
Chloride as Cl	4500-Cl. B	mg/L	41.36	41.01	34.74	42.35	41.03	-	250.00
Sulphate as SO ₄	4500- SO ₄ .E	mg/L	10.97	30.44	11.64	19.03	17.42	-	250.00
pH	4500- H ⁺ .B	-	7.17	7.61	7.22	7.17	7.21	0.18	6.50 – 8.50
Total Alkalinity	2320. B	mg/L	280.41	154.62	258.14	289.58	282.38	3.27	500.00
Calcium as CaCO ₃	3500-Ca. B	mg/L	181.98	108.12	142.39	142.39	134.71	2.47	250.00
Magnesium as Mg	3500- Mg. B	mg/L	74.44	57.91	98.08	112.26	100.52	-	

water pollution is anthropogenic activities, improper sanitation, and disposal of domestic and industrial solid-liquid

wastes. The excess amount of toxic chemicals and minerals from the above activities makes the water unsuitable for drinking, recreation, agricultural and industrial activities.

Water contamination alters humans, animals, fish, birds, and marine life, affect reproductive activities of the organism and causes carcinogenic diseases.

The results of the present research work show that the physic-chemical parameters such as pH, Na, Total hardness, Ca, Mg, Cl, Conductivity, T.D.S., T.S.S., and SO₄ of drinking water samples collected from different springs in the Sheringal area were found in permissible limit of W.H. O standard (Table.2) and can be used for drinking and irrigation purposes.

However, further study is also recommended for heavy metals and microbial analysis.

The present research also aims to inform the local community about water quality. The residents and local community will know to minimize water contamination by properly managing garbage and solid-liquid waste production and then their disposal at a particular site. Similarly, the use of fertilizers in agriculture should be properly governed to control heavy metals and other carcinogenic mineral accumulation. Proper purification techniques such as chlorination will prevent excess water contamination.

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